

Wild residue	Position	Target residue	Mut freq.	Mut (%)	PredictSNP prediction	PredictSNP expected accuracy	SNAP Prediction	SNAP expected accuracy	Annotations
C	1240	F	1	0.24	Deleterious	0.86908365	Deleterious	0.88519637	
V	826	L	1	0.24	Deleterious	0.7556615	Deleterious	0.62208185	
L	226	S	1	0.24	Deleterious	0.52145411	Deleterious	0.62208185	
C	1243	F	2	0.48	Deleterious	0.7556615	Deleterious	0.88519637	
S	221	L	2	0.48	Deleterious	0.50595948	Deleterious	0.62208185	
T	95	I	98	23.56	Deleterious	0.60697259	Deleterious	0.72038776	Natural variant: in strain: Iota/B.1.526, Mu/B.1.621, B.1.1.318, Omicron/BA.1 (mapped from position 95 in UniProt P0DTC2)
N	856	K	106	25.48	Deleterious	0.7556615	Deleterious	0.86956522	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1 (mapped from position 856 in UniProt P0DTC2)
N	764	K	151	36.30	Deleterious	0.71871275	Deleterious	0.72038776	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from

									position 764 in UniProt P0DTC2)
N	969	K	156	37.50	Deleterious	0.54946365	Deleterious	0.88519637	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 969 in UniProt P0DTC2)
Y	505	H	162	38.94	Deleterious	0.60697259	Deleterious	0.62208185	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 505 in UniProt P0DTC2)
L	452	R	249	59.86	Deleterious	0.65494636	Deleterious	0.72038776	Natural variant: in strain: Delta/B.1.617.2, Epsilon/B.1.427/B.1.429, Kappa/B.1.617.1, Lambda/C.37, 19B/501Y, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5;

									Contributes to cellular immunity evasion and increases infectivity (mapped from position 452 in UniProt P0DTC2)
Q	613	H	1	0.24	Neutral	0.62831343	Neutral	0.50014676	Natural variant: in strain: A23.1 (mapped from position 613 in UniProt P0DTC2)
S	704	L	1	0.24	Neutral	0.73834499	Neutral	0.61167883	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.2.12.1 (mapped from position 704 in UniProt P0DTC2)
P	26	L	1	0.24	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.70878378	
D	574	Y	1	0.24	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.58359402	
E	661	D	1	0.24	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.58359402	
I	693	V	1	0.24	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.70878378	
N	925	S	1	0.24	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.61167883	
R	214	L	1	0.24	Neutral	0.75291375	Deleterious	0.80510276	
V	62	I	1	0.24	Neutral	0.73834499	Neutral	0.66524217	
I	1210	V	1	0.24	Neutral	0.73834499	Neutral	0.66524217	
T	1117	I	1	0.24	Neutral	0.73688811	Deleterious	0.62208185	
G	1251	R	1	0.24	Neutral	0.62831343	Neutral	0.50014676	
S	256	L	1	0.24	Neutral	0.6025641	Deleterious	0.62208185	
V	915	I	1	0.24	Neutral	0.6025641	Deleterious	0.55551884	
D	1084	A	1	0.24	Neutral	0.6025641	Deleterious	0.72038776	

L	18	F	2	0.48	Neutral	0.68365861	Neutral	0.66524217	Natural variant: in strain: Beta/B.1.351, Gamma/P.1, 19B/501Y (mapped from position 18 in UniProt P0DTC2)
A	701	V	2	0.48	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.58359402	Natural variant: in strain: Beta/B.1.351, Iota/B.1.526 (mapped from position 701 in UniProt P0DTC2)
V	1176	F	2	0.48	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.66524217	Natural variant: in strain: Gamma/P.1, Theta/P.3, Zeta/P.2 (mapped from position 1176 in UniProt P0DTC2)
A	93	S	2	0.48	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.50014676	
V	171	I	2	0.48	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.58359402	
E	1262	D	2	0.48	Neutral	0.65307311	Neutral	0.61167883	
N	81	D	2	0.48	Neutral	0.62831343	Deleterious	0.84845361	
T	573	I	5	1.20	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.66524217	
G	446	V	5	1.20	Neutral	0.75291375	Deleterious	0.62208185	
Q	787	K	5	1.20	Neutral	0.73834499	Neutral	0.66524217	
K	1205	N	6	1.44	Neutral	0.73834499	Neutral	0.55439739	
T	19	R	46	11.06	Neutral	0.63151762	Deleterious	0.72038776	Natural variant: in strain: Delta/B.1.617.2, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1,

									Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 19 in UniProt P0DTC2)
V	213	G	50	12.02	Neutral	0.62831343	Deleterious	0.55551884	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 213 in UniProt P0DTC2)
T	376	A	51	12.26	Neutral	0.65307311	Deleterious	0.55551884	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 376 in UniProt P0DTC2)
R	408	S	51	12.26	Neutral	0.73688811	Deleterious	0.62208185	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 408 in UniProt P0DTC2)

S	371	F	51	12.26	Neutral	0.73834499	Neutral	0.55439739	
L	212	I	83	19.95	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.58359402	
G	446	S	89	21.39	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.58359402	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1 (mapped from position 446 in UniProt P0DTC2)
A	222	V	90	21.63	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.61167883	Natural variant: in strain: 20A.EU1 (mapped from position 222 in UniProt P0DTC2)
R	346	K	104	25.00	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.70878378	Natural variant: in strain: Mu/B.1.621 (mapped from position 346 in UniProt P0DTC2)
G	496	S	111	26.68	Neutral	0.63151762	Neutral	0.66524217	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1 (mapped from position 496 in UniProt P0DTC2)
T	547	K	111	26.68	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.55439739	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1 (mapped from position 547 in UniProt P0DTC2)
S	371	L	111	26.68	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.50014676	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1,

									Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 371 in UniProt P0DTC2)
K	417	N	137	32.93	Neutral	0.73834499	Neutral	0.70878378	Natural variant: in strain: Beta/B.1.351, Gamma/P.1, Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5; May enhance affinity to human ACE2 receptor (mapped from position 417 in UniProt P0DTC2)
N	440	K	138	33.17	Neutral	0.73688811	Neutral	0.58359402	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 440 in UniProt P0DTC2)
S	477	N	154	37.02	Neutral	0.82622462	Neutral	0.50014676	Natural variant: in strain: 20A.EU2, Iota/B.1.526, Omicron/BA.1,

									Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 477 in UniProt P0DTC2)
D	796	Y	156	37.50	Neutral	0.75203963	Neutral	0.58359402	Natural variant: in strain: 19B/501Y, Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 796 in UniProt P0DTC2)
Q	954	H	156	37.50	Neutral	0.73688811	Deleterious	0.55551884	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 954 in UniProt P0DTC2)
Q	493	R	161	38.70	Neutral	0.75203963	Deleterious	0.62208185	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2 Omicron/BA.2.12.1

									(mapped from position 493 in UniProt P0DTC2)
N	501	Y	162	38.94	Neutral	0.6025641	Neutral	0.55439739	Natural variant: in strain: Alpha/B.1.1.7, Beta/B.1.351, Gamma/P.1, Theta/P.3, Mu/B.1.621, 19B/501Y, Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5; May enhance affinity to human ACE2 receptor (mapped from position 501 in UniProt P0DTC2)
P	681	H	162	38.94	NEUTRAL	0.75291375	Deleterious	0.62208185	Natural variant: in strain: Alpha/B.1.1.7, Theta/P.3, Mu/B.1.621, B.1.1.318, A23.1, Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from

									position 681 in UniProt P0DTC2)
H	655	Y	162	38.94	NEUTRAL	0.73688811	Neutral	0.61167883	Natural variant: in strain: Gamma/P.1, 19B/501T, 19B/501Y, Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 655 in UniProt P0DTC2)
E	484	A	162	38.94	NEUTRAL	0.82622462	Neutral	0.58359402	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 484 in UniProt P0DTC2)
G	339	D	162	38.94	NEUTRAL	0.73834499	Neutral	0.58359402	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from

									position 339 in UniProt P0DTC2)
S	373	P	162	38.94	NEUTRAL	0.82622462	Neutral	0.55439739	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 373 in UniProt P0DTC2)
S	375	F	162	38.94	NEUTRAL	0.75203963	Deleterious	0.72038776	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 375 in UniProt P0DTC2)
Q	498	R	162	38.94	NEUTRAL	0.68365861	Deleterious	0.55551884	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 498 in UniProt P0DTC2)

N	679	K	162	38.94	NEUTRAL	0.82622462	Neutral	0.50014676	Natural variant: in strain: Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 679 in UniProt P0DTC2)
E	156	G	232	55.77	NEUTRAL	0.73834499	Deleterious	0.55551884	Natural variant: in strain: Delta/B.1.617.2 (mapped from position 156 in UniProt P0DTC2)
T	19	R	243	58.41	NEUTRAL	0.65307311	Deleterious	0.55551884	
D	950	N	249	59.86	NEUTRAL	0.82622462	Neutral	0.61167883	Natural variant: in strain: Delta/B.1.617.2, Mu/B.1.621 (mapped from position 950 in UniProt P0DTC2)
G	142	D	295	70.91	NEUTRAL	0.74796037	Deleterious	0.72038776	Natural variant: in strain: Kappa/B.1.617.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from

									position 142 in UniProt P0DTC2)
T	478	K	401	96.39	NEUTRAL	0.63151762	Deleterious	0.55551884	Natural variant: in strain: Delta/B.1.617.2, Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5 (mapped from position 478 in UniProt P0DTC2)
D	614	G	414	99.52	NEUTRAL	0.82622462	Neutral	0.58359402	Natural variant: in strain: Alpha/B.1.1.7, Beta/B.1.351, Gamma/P.1, Delta/B.1.617.2, Epsilon/B.1.427/B.1.429, Eta/B.1.525, Theta/P.3, Iota/B.1.526, Kappa/B.1.617.1, Lambda/C.37, B.1.1.318, Zeta/P.2, Mu/B.1.621, 20A.EU1, 20A.EU2, Omicron/BA.1, Omicron/BA.2, Omicron/BA.2.12.1, Omicron/BA.4, Omicron/BA.5;

									common variant; binds to hACE2 more efficiently; produces more infectious particles when cultured in primary human epithelial cells; does not significantly shift SARS-CoV-2 neutralization properties (mapped from position 614 in UniProt P0DTC2)
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S1 Table. List of PredictSNP SNP predictions in Negeri Sembilan from July 2021 – May 2022